

Energy-optimised cryogenic CO₂ capture for cement production decarbonisation: process design and techno-economic analysis

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Abstract

Achieving net-zero emissions in the cement sector requires the development of effective carbon capture technologies to address process-related emissions from limestone calcination. While much of the current research and applications focus on more conventional methods such as chemical absorption and oxyfuel, cryogenic CO₂ capture offers potential advantages in energy efficiency, capture rate, and product purity, though it remains underexplored at an industrial scale.

This study presents a comprehensive assessment of cryogenic CO₂ capture for cement applications in the EU, including thermodynamic modelling, process design and optimisation, and techno-economic analysis. Two process configurations targeting 90% and 95% capture at 99.9%_{mass} CO₂ purity are benchmarked. The 90% capture design achieves an energy penalty of 1.19 MJ_{el}/kgCO₂, corresponding to a threefold increase in electricity consumption compared to an unabated cement plant. Sensitivity analysis demonstrates consistent energy performance across a 17-28%_{mol} range of flue gas compositions. Increasing the capture rate from 90% to 95% maintains the energy penalty nearly constant (1.19-1.21 MJ_{el}/kgCO₂), with only marginal economic impact. At 95% capture, the incremental cost of clinker production rises by 5% compared to 90% capture, while the higher CO₂ avoidance yields a similar cost of avoided CO₂ (127-128 €/tCO₂).

From an economic perspective, cryogenic capture significantly outperforms conventional MEA-based capture, while remaining slightly less competitive than oxyfuel and calcium looping under current EU energy mix conditions. Overall, cryogenic capture emerges as an energy-efficient and economically viable post-combustion option for cement industry decarbonisation, with the added benefit of delivering a high-purity CO₂ stream suitable for storage or utilisation.

Keywords: *cement production, decarbonisation, cryogenic carbon capture, optimisation, techno-economic assessment.*

1. Introduction

The accumulation of greenhouse gases in the atmosphere, particularly carbon dioxide (CO₂), is a major driver of climate change. Among industrial sectors, the cement industry is the second-largest source of CO₂ emissions after iron and steel production, releasing approximately 2.4-2.5 GtCO₂ annually, equivalent to 6-7% of global emissions (IEA, 2023).

The most carbon-intensive stage of the cement supply chain is the production of clinker, the main constituent of cement. Approximately 60% of CO₂ emissions from this process result from the calcination reaction, in which limestone (CaCO₃) is decomposed into calcium oxide (CaO) and CO₂. The remaining emissions are associated with fossil fuel combustion – typically coal or natural gas – and electricity consumption for plant operations (Cavalett et al., 2024).

Several low-carbon strategies are available to reduce CO₂ emissions in the cement sector. These include carbon capture and storage (CCS) (Hills et al., 2016; Plaza et al., 2020), fossil fuels substitution with alternative fuels (Nhuchhen et al., 2021; Yang et al., 2021) or heat demand electrification (Madeddu et al., 2020), and reduction of the clinker-to-cement ratio (Miller et al., 2016; Knight et al., 2023). However, given the high share of unavoidable process emissions due to calcination, the deployment of CCS is essential to achieve net-zero targets. According to roadmaps by the International Energy Agency and the Global Cement and Concrete Association, CCS technologies will be responsible for avoiding 1.3-1.4 GtCO₂ annually by 2050 to align with net-zero goals for the cement sector (GCCA, 2021; IEA, 2023).

Different CCS technologies are being explored to support the decarbonisation of cement production, spanning both post-combustion and integrated configurations. Post-combustion options typically include solvent absorption, solid adsorption, and membrane separation, while integrated solutions comprise oxyfuel combustion and direct separation systems (Schneider et al., 2023). Calcium looping represents a hybrid solution, as it can be implemented in either a tail-end or integrated configuration (De Lena et al., 2019).

The techno-economic performance of these technologies has been assessed in several studies and demonstration projects. The CEMCAP project (CEMCAP, 2015) conducted a comprehensive evaluation of several technologies, including monoethanolamine (MEA) absorption, oxyfuel combustion, calcium looping, chilled ammonia process, and membrane-assisted CO₂ liquefaction. Among these, oxyfuel and calcium looping demonstrated the most promising performance (Gardarsdottir et al., 2019; Voldsund et al., 2019), leading further development in subsequent projects such as CLEANKER (2017), AC2OCEM (2019), and Catch4Climate (2020), which aimed to advance their technological readiness.

The direct separation concept has been investigated and demonstrated at pilot scale within the LEILAC (2016) and LEILAC2 (2020) projects. This technology enables to capture high-purity CO₂ released during calcination by indirectly heating limestone in the calciner, using multiple energy sources such as natural gas, biomass, or electricity. However, direct separation addresses only the emissions related to the cement calciner. To enable deeper decarbonisation, other studies explored integrating an electrified LEILAC-type calciner with MEA-based capture to treat the residual emissions from the rotary kiln (Quevedo Parra and Romano, 2023; Varnier et al., 2025).

While research and industrial deployment have largely focused on these established methods, cryogenic CO₂ capture (CCC) has gained increasing attention for its potential to achieve high capture rates and purities while maintaining low energy consumption (Font-Palma et al., 2021). In particular, the CCC process developed by Sustainable Energy Solutions and Chart Industries (Chart Industries, 2025) demonstrated promising energy performance, with energy penalties below 1 MJ_{el}/kgCO₂ (Jensen et al., 2015).

This CCC process is a post-combustion technology that separates CO₂ from flue gas by desublimation, converting CO₂ directly from gas to solid. This is achieved by contacting the flue gas with a liquid hydrocarbon at cryogenic temperatures between -130 °C and -110 °C, depending on the capture rate. The contact liquid ensures effective heat transfer, prevents CO₂ deposition on equipment surfaces, and allows solid CO₂ to be transported as a diluted slurry. Isopentane is typically selected

due to its low vapour pressure, which minimises evaporative losses and environmental risks (Jensen et al., 2015; Baxter et al., 2019). Most of the sensible heat is recovered via heat integration, meaning that only the energy for phase change and separation must be supplied via refrigeration cycles.

Due to its operating principle, CCC offers several advantages: it can efficiently achieve CO₂ purities above 99% and capture rates exceeding 90%. Unlike many conventional technologies, for which energy demand rises sharply at high capture rates, CCC maintains a moderate energy increase due to the narrow temperature differential (about 15 °C) between 90% and 99% capture (Baxter et al., 2019). In addition, the technology is fully electrifiable – ideally using renewable sources – and can be retrofitted with minimal disruption to existing plants (Baxter et al., 2021). Despite these promising features, CCC remains at an early stage of development. A pilot unit capturing 1 tCO₂/d has been successfully tested in the field (Frankman et al. 2021), while a 30 tCO₂/d demonstration plant is currently under development (Baxter et al., 2021), positioning the technology at Technology Readiness Level (TRL) of 5-6.

To promote broader interest and support future commercial deployment in cement industry applications, robust techno-economic assessments are essential. However, the techno-economic performance of CCC at a large scale remains underexplored in the literature, and most available studies focus on power-sector applications. Jensen et al. (2015) and Hoeger et al. (2021) evaluated CCC for a 550 MW_{el} coal-fired power plant, reporting energy penalties around 0.7-0.9 MJ_{el}/kgCO₂ and a 30 to 50% lower parasitic energy consumption compared to absorption technologies. Alsanousie et al. (2023) estimated a specific energy consumption of 0.83-0.88 MJ_{el}/kgCO₂ for integrating CCC with a 650 MW_{el} natural gas power plant. The only work specifically addressing the cement industry is by Asgharian et al. (2025), who assessed CCC with and without the integration of a water-ammonia absorption refrigeration cycle, reporting energy penalties of around 0.7 MJ_{el}/kgCO₂. Despite these efforts, the design choices and operating conditions adopted in literature are not comprehensively documented, and several aspects of process modelling rely on simplifications that weaken the reliability of reported results. For instance, a rigorous design of the flue-gas drying

section, critical for both energy and cost performance, is typically overlooked, and optimistic modelling assumptions, such as those related to turbomachinery efficiency or cooling water conditions, do not necessarily reflect realistic industrial scenarios.

Although refrigeration is a major driver of CCC energy demand (Asgharian et al. 2025), existing studies have not performed a systematic optimisation of refrigeration cycle operating conditions. A further limitation is the absence of a consistent comparison between CCC and alternative decarbonisation options using harmonised economic assumptions, in terms of CAPEX estimates and OPEX pricing.

To bridge these gaps and strengthen confidence in the CCC process, this work presents a comprehensive assessment of the technology tailored to cement industry applications in the European context. The objective is to enhance understanding of the CCC technical aspects and economic viability, while establishing a benchmark to guide future development and optimisation. In particular, the key contributions of the work are:

- Implementing a process optimisation strategy aimed at minimising process energy demand by identifying the optimal operating conditions of the refrigeration loop;
- Providing a rigorous design of the flue gas drying section, demonstrating its impact on energy and economic performance;
- Conducting sensitivity analyses on key variables such as flue gas composition, capture rate, and economic inputs to explore system potential and flexibility;
- Benchmarking CCC against alternative low-carbon technologies in the cement industry within a consistent economic framework, highlighting strengths, weaknesses, and trade-offs.

In addition, the study includes a dedicated discussion of system thermodynamics, with the development of an effective thermodynamic framework for simulating CCC within a standard process simulation environment.

2. Methods

This study presents the modelling, design and techno-economic assessment of two CCC configurations aimed at capturing 90% (CCC-90) and 95% (CCC-95) of CO₂ emissions from a coal-fired cement plant with a purity of 99.9%_{mass}. Both the cement plant and the capture process were simulated by solving steady-state material and energy balances using gPROMS Process 2024.1.0 software (Siemens, 2025). The simulation framework integrates standard gPROMS libraries with custom-developed unit models. Further information on the process modelling and custom models developed is provided in the following sections and the Supplementary Material.

2.1 Reference cement plant

The reference cement plant (Figure 1) is coal-fired and has a clinker production capacity of 3024 t_{clk}/d, equivalent to approximately 1 Mt_{clk}/y, based on an annual operating time of 8000 h. It employs a modern, energy-efficient dry process with a five-stage preheater-calciner kiln system equipped with a grate cooler. This process configuration reflects the Best Available Technique (BAT) for the cement industry, as defined in the European reference document (Schorcht et al., 2013).

The raw meal (stream #1 in Figure 1), composed of CaCO₃, SiO₂, Al₂O₃, Fe₂O₃ and MgCO₃, is dried and finely ground within the raw mill. The solid material is preheated to around 800°C via direct contact with hot gases from the calciner (stream #13) in the preheating tower. The cooled gas exits the tower at approximately 330 °C and is utilised to dry the raw meal before being released into the atmosphere. This flue gas (stream #15), characterised by a CO₂ concentration of 22.2%_{mol} and annual CO₂ emissions of 0.84 Mt_{CO₂}, constitutes the target stream for the CCC process. The preheated solids (stream #3) are calcined in the cement calciner, where CaCO₃ decomposes into CaO and CO₂ at high temperature (870°C). The heat to achieve this temperature and sustain the endothermic reaction is provided by the combustion of roughly 60% of the coal input (stream # 7) with kiln exhaust gas and tertiary air from the clinker cooler. The calcined material is further processed in the rotary kiln, where

the remaining share of coal is burned with secondary air, raising the temperature of the solid bed to 1450 °C and forming clinker (stream #5). The hot clinker is rapidly cooled to around 100°C with ambient air in the grate cooler to preserve its microstructure and make it suitable for storage. The hot air recovered from this cooling stage is reused in the process as secondary air for the kiln (stream #10) and tertiary air for the calciner (stream #11) and tertiary air for the calciner (stream #11).

Figure 1. Reference cement plant scheme: modern process with preheater-calciner system.

The modelling approach, along with key input parameters and assumptions for the reference cement plant, is described in detail in Varnier et al. (2025), while overall plant performance metrics are summarised in Table 1.

Table 1. Overall performance of the reference cement plant (Varnier et al., 2025).

Variable		Value
Clinker production	kg _{cl} /s	35.0
Total coal input	kg/t _{cl}	116.2
Total heat input	GJ _{LHV} /t _{cl}	3.128
Total electrical input	MWh _{el} /t _{cl}	0.132
Direct CO ₂ emissions	kg _{CO₂} /t _{cl}	833.1

2.2 CCC process summary

A simplified representation of the CCC process is shown in Figure 2. The flue gas from the cement plant (stream #1 in Figure 2), composed of CO₂, N₂, O₂, H₂O and Ar, first passes through a drying

section consisting of water scrubbing towers and a molecular sieve. Effective dehydration is essential to prevent ice formation, which could disrupt downstream cryogenic operations.

After drying, the gas is cooled near its desublimation point in a multi-stream heat exchanger and fed to the desublimation exchanger, where it is further cooled through direct contact with cold isopentane (stream #8). In this way, CO₂ is separated from the gas mixture primarily via desublimation and, to a minor extent, by dissolution in the contact liquid. The operating temperature in this unit ranges from -130 °C to -110 °C, depending on CO₂ concentration in the flue gas and the desired capture rate.

Figure 2. Block flow diagram of the cryogenic capture process investigated in the study.

The resulting slurry (stream #9), containing solid CO₂, liquid CO₂ and isopentane, is further cooled to increase the CO₂ solid content and to cool down the isopentane before its recirculation to the desublimation exchanger. The solid CO₂ is then separated from the liquid phase, melted, and fed to a distillation system, where residual isopentane is removed. The purified CO₂ (stream #14) is compressed to meet pipeline transportation specifications. The recovered isopentane (stream #16) is cooled and recycled to the desublimation exchanger together with that from the solid-liquid separator.

The cooling requirements of the process are met through heat integration in the multi-stream heat exchanger with the lean gas (stream #5), the liquid CO₂-rich stream (stream #12) and two external refrigeration loops. Both Refrigerant 1 and Refrigerant 2 are mixed hydrocarbon refrigerants, including methane, ethylene, propane and n-butane, commonly used in natural gas liquefaction.

2.3 Thermodynamic modelling

The CCC system involves several separation steps that rely on direct contact between process streams and heat exchange at cryogenic temperatures. In this context, the implementation of a thermodynamic model capable of accurately predicting both phase equilibria and specific heat capacities across a broad range of temperatures and pressures is crucial for reliable process simulation and design.

In particular, accurate modelling of solid-liquid-vapour equilibria (SLVE) between CO₂ and isopentane is essential for correctly simulating CO₂ desublimation from the flue gas, the core step of the process. Similarly, vapour-liquid equilibria (VLE) must be precisely represented for operations such as drying and CO₂-isopentane distillation. In addition, reliable heat capacity predictions are necessary to accurately perform energy balances and estimate the overall process energy demand. To meet these requirements, the volume-translated Peng-Robinson (VTPR) equation of state (Ahlers and Gmehling, 2002) was selected as the thermodynamic model.

Figure 3 compares VTPR equilibrium predictions with experimental data from the literature for the CO₂-H₂O and CO₂-isopentane systems (Kurata, 1974; Besserer and Robinson, 1975; Dalmolin et al., 2006). These binary systems are of particular interest, as they refer to key separations in the process: water scrubbing for flue gas drying, CO₂ desublimation, and CO₂-isopentane distillation. VTPR adequately reproduces CO₂ solubility in water (Figure 3a), CO₂-isopentane solid-liquid equilibria (SLE) (Figure 3b), and CO₂-isopentane VLE (Figure 3c), confirming its suitability for CCC process simulation. Furthermore, for the same systems, it was observed that VTPR generally yields better performance compared to the conventional Peng-Robinson (PR) equation of state, which has been adopted in previous studies on CCC (Jensen et al., 2015; Asgharian et al., 2025).

Figure 3. Phase equilibria prediction obtained by volume-translated Peng-Robinson (VTPR) equation of state against experimental data (●: Dalmolin et al., (2006); ■: Kurata, (1974); ▲: Besserer and Robinson (1975)). (a) P-x diagram for vapour-liquid equilibria of CO₂-H₂O system at 25°C; (b) T-x diagram for solid-liquid equilibria of CO₂-isopentane system at 4 bar; (c) P-x diagram for vapour-liquid equilibria of CO₂-isopentane system at 4.4°C.

Despite the accurate representation of equilibrium, the VTPR model, like PR and other cubic equations of state, generally performs poorly in predicting liquid heat capacities (c_P^{liq}) of pure substances, as these are based on temperature-dependent correlations tied to critical properties. This limitation was highlighted by Diedrichs et al. (2006), who demonstrated that improved predictions can be obtained by using the modified α -function proposed by Twu et al. (1991):

$$\alpha(T) = \left(\frac{T}{T_{cr}}\right)^{l_2 \cdot (l_1 - 1)} \cdot \exp\left\{l_0 \cdot \left[1 - \left(\frac{T}{T_{cr}}\right)^{l_2 \cdot l_1}\right]\right\} \quad (1)$$

where T is the temperature, T_{cr} is the critical temperature of the component, and l_0 , l_1 , and l_2 are component-specific parameters fitted simultaneously to vapour pressure (P^{sat}) and c_P^{liq} data. An accurate representation of ideal gas heat capacity (c_P^{ig}) is a prerequisite for this approach.

Following Diedrichs et al. (2006), parameters l_0 , l_1 , and l_2 were fitted to P^{sat} and c_P^{liq} data for the liquid species, namely CO₂, isopentane, methane, ethylene, propane, n-butane and H₂O. For this purpose, pseudo-experimental data were retrieved from the NIST Chemistry WebBook (Linstrom and Mallard, 2001). For isopentane, the c_P^{ig} default correlation in gPROMS Properties was found to overestimate values below -75 °C, and was therefore replaced by a second-order polynomial fit:

$$c_P^{ig}(T) = c_0 + c_1 \cdot T + c_2 \cdot T^2 \quad (2)$$

where T is temperature, and c_0 , c_1 , and c_2 are fitting parameters. The fitted parameters and applicable temperature ranges are summarised in Table 2.

Table 2. Fitted α -function and c_P^{ig} parameters for selected species.

Species	α -function parameters (Eq. 1)			T range P^{sat} data [K]	T range c_P^{liq} data [K]
	l_0	l_1	l_2		
CO ₂	0.03618	0.92685	7.00758	217-303	218-270
H ₂ O	0.47230	0.87413	1.66156	280-640	280-340
Isopentane	0.39582	0.83631	1.41874	140-460	140-370
Methane	0.03915	0.95112	5.33812	91-190	130-170
Ethylene	0.15696	0.86382	1.87515	104-282	130-240
Propane	0.47351	0.85852	1.07838	120-368	130-300
n-Butane	0.52644	0.85205	1.09632	139-425	136-300
	c_P^{ig} parameters (Eq. 2)			T range c_P^{ig} data [K]	
	c_0	$c_1 \cdot 10^1$	$c_2 \cdot 10^5$		
Isopentane	10.4680	3.90228	-8.72744	130-500	

Figure 4 illustrates the impact of these modifications for n-butane, comparing the c_P^{liq} results of the standard PR, standard VTPR, and the VTPR with modified α -function against experimental data. Both the standard PR and VTPR models yield poor predictions of n-butane c_P^{liq} : PR significantly underestimates heat capacity across the full temperature range, while the standard VTPR deviates notably below -95 °C. Such discrepancies would introduce substantial errors in heat balance

calculations. In contrast, the VTPR model with the modified α -function provides significantly improved performance, making it more suitable for accurate process simulations.

After implementing these modifications, it was verified that phase equilibrium predictions and gas-phase heat capacities remained unaffected or slightly improved. These results, along with the detailed fitting procedure, are provided in the Supplementary Material.

Figure 4. Comparison of liquid heat capacity prediction for *n*-butane at 35 bar obtained by standard volume-translated Peng-Robinson (VTPR), standard Peng-Robinson (PR), and VTPR with modified α -function, against experimental data from Linstrom and Mallard (2001).

Finally, for pure water used in the process (e.g., in water coolers), thermodynamic properties were calculated using the IAPWS-95 model (Wagner and Pruß, 2002), the reference standard for pure water property calculations.

2.4 CCC process modelling

The CCC process evaluated in this study is based on the design proposed by Sustainable Energy Solutions and Chart Industries (Chart Industries, 2025) and is further adapted from the implementation described by Asgharian et al. (2025). The CCC configurations assessed are designed to capture 90% (CCC-90) and 95% (CCC-95) of the CO₂ contained in the flue gas emitted by the reference cement plant, whose properties are provided in Table 3. Pollutants such as SO_x, NO_x, HCl, CO and H₂S are excluded from the analysis due to their low concentrations. The processes are

simulated assuming that cooling water is available at 25°C and considering an electrical-to-mechanical efficiency of 95%.

Table 3. Properties and composition of reference cement plant flue gas (Varnier et al., 2025).

Variable		Value
Mass flowrate	kg/s	91.71
Temperature	°C	110.0
Pressure	bar	1.0
Molar composition		
O ₂	% mol wet	6.9
N ₂	% mol wet	58.2
CO ₂	% mol wet	22.2
H ₂ O	% mol wet	12.1
Ar	% mol wet	0.7

The detailed process flow diagram of the CCC plant is shown in Figure 5, while the following sections describe the modelling approach and the key process assumptions for each subsystem.

Figure 5. Process flow diagram of the cryogenic capture process investigated in the study. DCC: direct contact cooler; HX: heat exchanger (water-cooled); DRY1: water scrubbing tower; DRY2: water cooling tower; MOL SIEVE: molecular sieve; e-HEATER: electric heater; MSHX: multi-stream heat exchanger; DES: desublimation exchanger; PUM: pump; SL-SEP: solid-liquid separator; DIST: distillation tower; CO₂ COMP: CO₂ compressor; R1 COMP: refrigerant 1 compressor; R2 COMP: refrigerant 2 compressor.

2.4.1 Flue gas drying section

The flue gas exits the cement plant at 110°C (stream #1, Figure 5) and supplies heat in the distillation column reboiler, vaporising the residue. This heat integration avoids the need for low/medium-pressure steam and related utility management, but constrains the distillation CO₂ recovery, as part of the CO₂ is lost in the residue to maintain a feasible temperature difference for heat exchange. Afterwards, the flue gas enters the drying section, which is essential to prevent ice formation in the multi-stream heat exchanger (MSHX) and to avoid water accumulation in the process. The first stage consists of a direct contact cooler (DCC), where the gas is scrubbed with cooling water to reduce its temperature to 30°C and to lower the water content to approximately 6%_{mol}. Complete dehydration is achieved through further scrubbing with chilled water, followed by a final drying stage using a molecular sieve, as detailed below.

The cooled gas (stream #3) is then compressed in the BLOWER to approximately 1.5 bar to compensate for downstream pressure losses, mainly related to the final dehydration step in the molecular sieve. The BLOWER, assumed to have an isentropic efficiency of 80%, is strategically placed after the DCC to treat a lower gas volumetric flowrate and improve energy efficiency. The compressed gas is cooled in heat exchanger HX1 to near-ambient conditions before entering an absorption column (DRY1), where chilled water reduces the residual water content below 1.5%_{mol}. This step reduces the required adsorption capacity of the molecular sieve beds.

The chilled water for DRY1 is regenerated in a cooling tower (DRY2) through a fraction of the cold and dry lean gas (stream #15), which leaves the MSHX at 10°C and cools the water exiting DRY1 before recirculation. A small blowdown (stream #12) is introduced to prevent water accumulation in the closed loop between DRY1 and DRY2. As detailed in the Supplementary Material, the blowdown fraction is set to 0.015, which minimises the temperature of the gas exiting DRY1 (stream #6). The DCC, DRY1 and DRY2 towers are modelled as packed columns consisting of 5, 6 and 6 equilibrium stages, respectively. Metal Pall® rings of 50 mm (2 inch) are employed as packing material, and the column pressure drop is estimated with gPROMS built-in hydraulic models.

The final drying step reduces water content to trace levels (around 1 ppmv) through a temperature swing adsorption (TSA) system employing molecular sieves. Zeolite 3A is selected due to its higher selectivity for H₂O over CO₂ and its lower regeneration temperature compared to zeolite 4A (Kohl and Nielsen, 1997). A custom model was developed to simulate and size the TSA unit, with two objectives: (i) determining the required adsorbent mass and bed dimensions to meet the separation target within the specified pressure drop and (ii) estimating the thermal effect of the exothermic water adsorption, which impacts downstream cooling requirements. The maximum allowable pressure drop was set at 0.35 bar, corresponding to the lower end of the design range suggested by Kohl and Nielsen (1997), due to its strong influence on the overall energy consumption. Further modelling details and design parameters are provided in the Supplementary Material (Kohl and Nielsen, 1997; Simo et al., 2009; Cinti et al., 2018; Towler and Sinnott, 2021).

Accounting for the bed regeneration phase is essential to avoid underestimating the TSA energy demand. During regeneration, a portion of the dry lean gas exiting the MSHX, equivalent to 10% of the dried flue gas (stream #17), is diverted and heated to 250 °C, as reported by IEAGHG (2011). The regeneration gas is circulated by a fan (not shown in Figure 5) and heated in an electric heater (e-HEATER), in line with the full electrification scenario adopted in this study. This approach reflects a conservative assumption in which no waste heat is available from the cement plant. The energy demand for regeneration is calculated assuming 99.5% power-to-heat efficiency (Element Energy, 2018) and a heating phase covering 60% of the cycle time (Kohl and Nielsen, 1997).

2.4.2 CO₂ capture section

The dehydrated gas (stream #7) is cooled near the desublimation point (-94°C) by refrigerants and cold process streams within the MSHX. The gas then enters the desublimation exchanger (DES), where it comes into direct contact with isopentane (stream #21) fed at an extremely low temperature (-121°C). The isopentane serves as a heat transfer medium and as a source of nucleation sites, promoting CO₂ desublimation from the flue gas, with minor additional capture via dissolution. The

capture rate is determined entirely by the coldest temperature reached by the gas: for a 90% capture rate and the investigated flue gas composition, the lean gas exits the DES at -113°C .

According to technology developers (Baxter et al., 2019), this unit is designed as a hybrid spray-bubble tower: flue gas bubbles through a hold-up of isopentane at the bottom, while liquid droplets capture the remaining CO_2 at the top. A detailed simulation of such a system would require a distributed model with mass and heat transfer based on column hydraulics, which is beyond the scope of this study. Instead, following the approach suggested by Asgharian et al. (2025), the DES is modelled as a series of five equilibrium stages in which gPROMS computes SLVE, with a pressure drop per stage of 0.003 bar.

The lean gas (stream #14) is reheated to 10°C and subsequently used for adsorption bed regeneration and chilled water production, as described in Section 2.4.1. The CO_2 /isopentane slurry formed (stream #22) is a diluted slurry, with a solid mass fraction of approximately $6\%_{\text{mass}}$. It is pressurised above the CO_2 triple point (5.17 bar) in a centrifugal pump PUM1 (Baxter et al., 2019) to maintain liquid CO_2 in the downstream stages, and further cooled down in the SLURRY COOLER. This additional cooling increases the overall solid content to nearly $9\%_{\text{mass}}$ prior to solid-liquid separation, and reduces the isopentane temperature before it is recycled to the DES. The outlet temperature of the SLURRY COOLER is set to -124°C for CCC-90, consistent with the typical operating range reported in previous studies (Baxter et al., 2019; Asgharian et al., 2025). Once this outlet temperature is fixed, the capture rate is uniquely determined by the contact liquid flowrate entering the DES (stream #21). For CCC-95, the capture rate is set to 95% by decreasing the SLURRY COOLER outlet temperature while keeping the flowrate to DES fixed at the CCC-90 value of 289.6 kg/s.

2.4.3 CO_2 /isopentane purification section

The cold slurry undergoes solid-liquid separation and distillation steps to achieve the target CO_2 purity. The proper assessment of the solid-liquid separator (SL-SEP) would require experimental data on CO_2 particle size distribution under CCC operating conditions, which are currently unavailable.

Early designs proposed a hydrocyclone followed by a continuous press filter (Jensen et al., 2015), while later documentation described a screw-press system (Baxter et al., 2019). The most recent source reports a proprietary filter capable of separating CO₂ solids from the isopentane-rich liquid with 95% efficiency (Asgharian et al., 2025). In this work, the latter configuration is adopted as the best available representation of current practice, therefore assuming 5% of the inlet liquid is lost with the solid phase. Further experimental studies are recommended to support a more accurate design of the solid-liquid separator.

The recovered isopentane-rich liquid (stream #35), still containing traces of CO₂, is recycled to the DES, while the concentrated slurry (stream #25) is heated to -58°C in the MELTER to fully melt CO₂ while avoiding vaporisation that could cause operating problems in pump PUM2.

The CO₂-rich stream is brought to ambient temperature by heat recovery in the MSHX, before entering the distillation column (DIST) as a liquid-vapour mixture (stream #28). The distillation is performed at 24 bar in a column comprising 11 ideal stages, with the feed introduced above stage 9, producing CO₂ at 99.9%_{mass} purity. The reboiler is operated at 100°C to maintain a 10°C minimum approach with the incoming flue gas, thereby fixing the CO₂ recovery at a given pressure. A detailed discussion on the selection of distillation pressure and number of stages is provided in the Supplementary Material.

DIST operates with a partial condenser, collecting the pure CO₂ in the vapour phase. To meet transportation requirements, CO₂ is compressed to 80 bar, condensed, and further pressurised to 110 bar through the pump PUM3 (stream #31). A partial condenser was preferred over a total condenser due to the significantly lower cooling demand. Under design conditions (24 bar), the partial condenser requires 1.86 MW_{th} against 9.00 MW_{th} for complete condensation. Moreover, total condensation of CO₂ below 65 bar would necessitate refrigeration, as the condensation temperature is incompatible with standard cooling water. To avoid this energy-intensive requirement, the process design favours higher compression work over refrigeration.

The isopentane-rich stream collected as residue (stream #32) is cooled in HX2, further chilled in the MSHX to -83°C (just above the solidification limit), and recycled to the DES. A small isopentane make-up (stream #36) compensates for minor system losses.

2.4.4 Refrigerant loops

The process cooling requirements are provided by two refrigerant loops. Refrigerant 1 (stream #37) consists of a hydrocarbon mixture containing methane, ethylene, propane, and n-butane, and delivers cooling to both the MSHX and the SLURRY COOLER. It is compressed in an 8-stage compressor (isentropic efficiency: 85%) with a constant pressure ratio and intercooling to 30°C , condensed in the MSHX, and expanded through a valve to supply cooling to the SLURRY COOLER. The expansion pressure is selected to maintain a minimum temperature approach of 5°C at the SLURRY COOLER outlet. Refrigerant 1 flowrate, composition, condensation temperature and pressure are determined through the process optimisation presented in Section 2.6. Refrigerant 2 (stream #42) loop does not provide active cooling, but instead acts as a thermal transfer medium, redistributing the heat released during CO_2 melting to the distillation condenser and the MSHX. As this loop contributes minimally to the overall energy demand, it is not subject to optimisation. Refrigerant 2 is a binary mixture composed of 80%_{mass} ethylene and 20%_{mass} methane, while its flowrate is adjusted to ensure condensation in the MELTER (stream #44) at -100°C . Afterwards, it is used to operate the distillation condenser, expanded to -84°C , evaporated in MSHX and recompressed to 13 bar. Due to the low-pressure differential and flowrate, the isentropic efficiency of Refrigerant 2 compressor is set to 75%.

2.4.5 Heat exchangers

The type of exchangers adopted is detailed in the Supplementary Material, which includes further design considerations. Pressure drop and minimum temperature approach (ΔT_{min}) in heat exchangers are defined based on literature data and industrial design practices. For gas streams, a pressure drop of 0.1 bar is assumed in compressor intercoolers, 1% of inlet pressure in MSHX (ESDU, 2003), and

2% of inlet pressure in other heat exchangers (Anantharaman et al., 2017). For liquids or biphasic mixtures, the pressure drop is set to 0.1 bar in MSHX (ESDU, 2003) and 0.2 bar in other units. These values are consistent with the ranges reported by Jensen et al. (2015) for industrial exchangers applied to the CCC process.

Regarding thermal design, a ΔT_{min} of 5°C was applied for liquid-liquid heat exchange and compressor intercoolers, while 10°C was used for liquid-gas systems. Biphasic mixtures were treated following the same criteria as the liquid phase. For the MSHX, a ΔT_{min} of 2°C was adopted, consistent with reported values as low as 1°C for this unit (ESDU, 2003).

2.5 KPIs and economic analysis

The performance of the CCC process is evaluated through a series of KPIs, as detailed in the following. The energy penalty (γ [MJ_{el}/kg_{CO₂}]) is the primary metric to quantify the CCC process energy efficiency, given its fully electrified nature:

$$\gamma = \frac{\dot{W}_{el}^{CCC}}{\dot{m}_{CO_2,capt}} \quad (3)$$

where \dot{W}_{el}^{CCC} [MW_{el}] denotes the total electrical power consumed exclusively by the CCC process, while $\dot{m}_{CO_2,capt}$ [kg_{CO₂}/s] is the mass flowrate of captured CO₂.

The equivalent specific CO₂ emissions ($e_{eq,clk}$ [kg_{CO₂}/t_{clk}]) are calculated as:

$$e_{eq,clk} = e_{clk} + e_{el,clk} \quad (4)$$

where e_{clk} represents direct CO₂ emissions (Scope 1) and $e_{el,clk}$ reflects indirect CO₂ emissions associated with the electricity supplied to the plant (Scope 2). The latter is determined by multiplying the overall electrical demand of the process, including the cement plant ($\dot{W}_{el,clk}$ [MWh_{el}/t_{clk}]) by the carbon intensity of the imported electricity (e_{el} [kg_{CO₂}/MWh_{el}]):

$$e_{el,clk} = \dot{W}_{el,clk} \cdot e_{el} \quad (5)$$

The carbon capture rate (CCR [%]) indicates the CO_2 capture efficiency by measuring the amount of carbon effectively captured (and sent to storage) by the CCC process relative to the total amount generated by the reference cement plant, excluding indirect emissions. It is defined as:

$$CCR = \frac{e_{capt,clk}}{e_{capt,clk} + e_{clk}} \cdot 100 \quad (6)$$

where $e_{capt,clk}$ [kg_{CO_2}/t_{clk}] is the amount of CO_2 captured. The equivalent CO_2 avoidance rate (AC_{eq} [%]) quantifies the reduction in equivalent CO_2 emissions between a cement plant equipped with CCC and an unabated reference plant:

$$AC_{eq} = \left(1 - \frac{e_{eq,clk}^{CCC}}{e_{eq,clk}^{ref}} \right) \cdot 100 \quad (7)$$

where the superscript “CCC” refers to the plant with cryogenic carbon capture, and “ref” to the unabated reference plant.

Two scenarios are evaluated for the carbon intensity of imported electricity, consistent with the authors’ previous work (Varnier et al., 2025). The first scenario reflects the EU-27 energy mix in 2022, with $e_{el} = 258 \text{ kg}_{CO_2}/MWh_{el}$ (EEA, 2025). The second scenario assumes electricity supplied entirely from non-combustible renewables (wind, solar and hydro), thus setting $e_{el} = 0 \text{ kg}_{CO_2}/MWh_{el}$. Notably, the latter value excludes upstream emissions associated with the electricity supply chain.

The economic KPIs include the increment in cost of clinker (ΔCOC [$\text{€}/t_{clk}$]) and cost of avoided CO_2 (CAC [$\text{€}/t_{CO_2}$]). As CCC is a post-combustion retrofit, ΔCOC considers only capital expenditures (CAPEX) and operating costs ($OPEX$ [$\text{€}/y$]) related to capture system. The CAC represents the additional expenditure required to avoid 1 t of equivalent CO_2 compared to the reference plant, reflecting the breakeven carbon tax under the considered economic conditions. The cost formulations are as follows:

$$\Delta COC = COC^{CCC} - COC^{ref} = \frac{TAC^{CCC} + OPEX^{CCC}}{\dot{m}_{clk}} \quad (8)$$

$$CAC = \frac{COC^{CCC} - COC^{ref}}{e_{eq,clk}^{ref} - e_{eq,clk}^{CCC}} = \frac{\Delta COC}{e_{eq,clk}^{ref} - e_{eq,clk}^{CCC}} \quad (9)$$

where TAC [€/y] is the total annualised CAPEX and \dot{m}_{clk} [t_{clk}/y] is the annual clinker productivity. The economic analysis follows the same methodology used in the authors' previous study (Varnier et al., 2025), including assumptions for CAPEX estimation and OPEX pricing. All costs are expressed in €₂₀₂₄, adjusted using the CEPCI for January 2024, which is 795.4 (Chemical Engineering, 2024), with exchange rates of 0.91 €/€ and 1.18 €/£. The baseline CAC calculations assume a grid carbon intensity of 258 kgCO₂/MWh_{el} for the EU-27 in 2022.

A bottom-up approach, typical of preliminary cost analysis, is employed to estimate the CAPEX (Rubin et al., 2013). As illustrated in Figure 6, this consists of determining the total overnight cost (TOC [€]) of the plant, starting from the equipment cost of each process unit j (EC [€]).

Figure 2. Schematics of calculation procedure to estimate plant CAPEX.

The estimation of EC for an individual unit is based on its key design variables derived from process simulations and using cost correlations sourced from scientific literature, industry reports, and engineering handbooks. A suitable installation factor (IF [–]) is applied to EC to determine the bare erected cost (BEC [€]) of the equipment, accounting for the installation cost. A detailed survey of equipment sizing methodologies, cost correlations and installation factors used in this study is provided in the Supplementary Material (Picón-Núñez et al., 2002; ESDU, 2003; Peters et al., 2003; Shah and Sekulic, 2003; Cinti et al., 2018; Element Energy, 2018; Turton et al., 2018; De Lena et al., 2019; Towler and Sinnott, 2021; Asgharian et al., 2025).

A process contingency of 40% of the *BEC* is applied to all CCC process units yielding the total direct cost (*TDC* [€]) of the unit. This process contingency reflects the current status of the technology with small pilot plant data (Rubin et al., 2013). To obtain the total plant cost (*TPC* [€]) of each item, indirect costs (14% of *TDC*) and project contingencies (20% of *TDC*) are added, consistent with assumptions from Varnier et al. (2025). The overall CAPEX is obtained by summing the *TPC* of all units and adding owner's costs (10% of total *TPC*), which cover, for instance, land, inventory, and start-up expenses. Finally, the *TOC* are annualised to *TAC* with Equation 10, assuming a 25-year plant operational life (*n*) and an 8% discount rate (*i*):

$$TAC = TOC \cdot \frac{i(1+i)^n}{(1+i)^n - 1} \quad (10)$$

The OPEX are divided into fixed and variable components, and are calculated based on the assumptions summarised in Table 4.

Table 4. Assumptions for OPEX calculation.

Fixed OPEX			Reference
Local taxes/insurance	%TPC/y	2.0	Gardarsdottir et al. (2019)
Maintenance	%TPC/y	2.5	"
Personnel in reference plant	-	100	"
Additional personnel in capture plant	-	20	"
Labour Cost	€/y per personnel	60000	"
Maintenance labour (<i>ML</i>)	% Maintenance	40	"
Administrative/support labour	%(OL + ML)	30	"
Variable OPEX			Reference
Electricity	€/MWh _{el}	125.0	Eurostat (2025)
Cooling water	€/m ³	0.02	Cormos (2022)
Isopentane	€/t _{isop}	1200.0	ChemAnalyst (2025)
CO ₂ Transport and Storage	€/t _{CO₂,prod}	35.0	d'Amore et al. (2021)

The operating labour cost (*OL* [€/y]) is calculated by multiplying the labour cost by the number of employees at the plant. The additional personnel value is based on values reported for CO₂ capture projects of comparable scale in the cement sector (Gardarsdottir et al., 2019). *OL* and maintenance labour (*ML* [€/y]), assumed to represent 40% of total maintenance cost, contribute to the estimation of administrative/support labour costs.

The study does not assume a specific geographical location for the plant. The transport and storage costs reported are representative of an optimised European CCS supply chain, in which CO₂ is transported primarily via pipelines, complemented by ship transport (d'Amore et al., 2021).

2.6 Energy penalty optimisation framework

Given the fully electrified nature of the CCC system, process optimisation is essential to minimise electricity consumption. An energy-based optimisation approach was adopted rather than an economic one, due to the significant uncertainties associated with CAPEX estimates in early-stage CCS projects, which may render economic evaluations unreliable. Furthermore, as will be shown in the results, the energy efficiency largely drives economic performance, since total electricity demand and the Refrigerant 1 compressor CAPEX are the main cost contributors.

The optimisation targets the minimisation of the process energy penalty by identifying the optimal operating conditions of the Refrigerant 1 loop, which accounts for approximately 75% of the total electricity consumption, as the results will show. The decision variables include the flowrates of each Refrigerant 1 component, condensation pressure (i.e., pressure of stream #38 in Figure 5), and temperature (i.e., temperature of stream #39 in Figure 5). These variables, along with their corresponding bounds in the CCC-90 case, are listed in Table 5. The optimisation is subject to technical constraints, including the ΔT_{min} in the MSHX and SLURRY COOLER.

The optimisation problem was implemented in gPROMS and solved using the Non-Linear Programming Multi-Start Optimiser (NLPMSO). This solver performs multiple local searches with a Sequential Quadratic Programming (SQP) algorithm, each starting from a different initial guess within defined bounds, and selects the best result among the local optima identified. The use of NLPMSO was motivated by preliminary optimisation results, which revealed a complex design space characterised by multiple local optima with comparable objective function values. The multi-start approach increases the likelihood of identifying a solution near the global optimum. Using 32 initial

points was found to provide a good compromise between computational time (around 30 minutes) and solution quality.

Table 5. Process optimisation formulation: objective function, decision variables (with bounds for the configuration at 90% capture rate (CCC-90), and constraints.

Objective function			
$\min \gamma = \frac{\dot{W}_{el}^{CCC}}{\dot{m}_{CO_2,capt}}$			
Decision variables		Lower bound	Upper bound
Flowrate methane Refrigerant 1	kg/s	20	35
Flowrate ethylene Refrigerant 1	kg/s	25	40
Flowrate propane Refrigerant 1	kg/s	0	10
Flowrate n-butane Refrigerant 1	kg/s	15	28
Condensation pressure Refrigerant 1	bar	30	40
Condensation temperature Refrigerant 1	°C	-103	-99
Constraints			
$\Delta T_{min} \text{ MSHX} \geq 2^\circ\text{C}$			
$\Delta T_{min} \text{ SLURRY COOLER} \geq 5^\circ\text{C}$			

3. Results and discussion

3.1 Technical results

The technical results for the optimised CCC-90 and CCC-95 configurations are summarised in Table 6. For CCC-90, the Refrigerant 1 loop operates with a total flowrate of 80.35 kg/s, comprising 42.2%_{mass} methane, 32.4%_{mass} ethylene, and 25.4%_{mass} n-butane. The refrigerant is compressed to approximately 37 bar and condensed to -101°C in the MSHX before being expanded to deliver the cooling duty in the SLURRY COOLER. For the higher capture rate of CCC-95, the optimal refrigerant loop features an increased total flowrate (82.55 kg/s), a composition richer in heavier components, and lower condensation pressure and temperature. In both cases, propane is excluded from the mixture.

For CCC-90, the power consumption is 31.26 MW_{el}, corresponding to an energy penalty of 1.19 MJ_{el}/kgCO₂. Increasing the capture rate to 95% raises the power demand to 33.41 MW_{el}, driven by higher process flowrates and the lower temperature required in the desublimation exchanger.

Nevertheless, the energy penalty increases only marginally to 1.21 MJ_{el}/kgCO₂. As will be shown in the capture rate sensitivity analysis (Section 3.1.1), this limited increase is due to the fixed energy required for drying, which is independent of the capture rate and largely offsets the additional specific consumption of the Refrigerant 1 loop.

Table 6. Summary of simulation results for the optimal cryogenic capture process at 90% capture rate (CCC-90) and 95% capture rate (CCC-95).

Process variables		CCC-90	CCC-95		
CO ₂ captured	kg/s	26.244	27.702		
Cooling water consumption	m ³ /s	1.125	1.182		
Isopentane make-up	kg/s	0.0206	0.0190		
Optimal decision variables					
Flowrate methane Refrigerant 1	kg/s	33.90	33.59		
Flowrate ethylene Refrigerant 1	kg/s	26.05	27.40		
Flowrate propane Refrigerant 1	kg/s	0.00	0.00		
Flowrate n-butane Refrigerant 1	kg/s	20.40	21.56		
Condensation pressure Refrigerant 1	bar	36.91	35.77		
Condensation temperature Refrigerant 1	°C	-101.04	-102.53		
Electrical power consumption		Share		Share	
Blower	MW _{el}	3.95	12.6%	3.95	11.8%
e-Heater	MW _{el}	1.27	4.1%	1.27	3.8%
Refrigerant 1 compressor	MW _{el}	23.17	74.1%	25.18	75.4%
Refrigerant 2 compressor	MW _{el}	0.55	1.8%	0.58	1.7%
CO ₂ compression (CO ₂ COMP + PUM3)	MW _{el}	1.90	6.1%	2.01	6.0%
Pumps (PUM1 + PUM2)	MW _{el}	0.41	1.3%	0.42	1.2%
Total electricity (\dot{W}_{el}^{CCC})	MW_{el}	31.26	100.0%	33.41	100.0%
Energy penalty (γ)	MJ_{el}/kgCO₂	1.19	-	1.21	-

In both cases, the Refrigerant 1 compression is the dominant contributor to the energy demand, accounting for 74-75% of the total, followed by the BLOWER (12-13%) that compensates for pressure drops across the drying section. The e-HEATER used for molecular sieve regeneration adds a further 4%, making the drying section responsible for nearly 17% of total power consumption. This estimate excludes the energy required to compensate for the thermal effects associated with water adsorption, which is not easily quantifiable. The energy required for CO₂ compression to pipeline pressure, including both the compressor and the pump, is modest, contributing around 6% of the total. This is facilitated by pumping liquid-phase CO₂ to 24 bar upstream of the distillation column, which significantly reduces CO₂ compression work. The energy demand associated with the Refrigerant 2 loop and other pumping systems plays a marginal role in the overall expenses.

The CCC energy efficiency is promising when compared to conventional MEA-based carbon capture. This process incurs both a thermal energy penalty of $3.76 \text{ MJ}_{\text{th}}/\text{kgCO}_2$ and an electrical energy penalty of $0.52 \text{ MJ}_{\text{el}}/\text{kgCO}_2$ for a cement plant flue gas with a similar CO_2 concentration and for the same *CCR* (Voldsund et al., 2019).

At 90% capture, the electrical energy penalty estimated in this work ($1.19 \text{ MJ}_{\text{el}}/\text{kgCO}_2$) is considerably higher than the $0.7 \text{ MJ}_{\text{el}}/\text{kgCO}_2$ reported by Asgharian et al. (2025), representing a 72% increase. This discrepancy arises from several differences in modelling approaches and assumptions. In Asgharian et al. (2025), the final water removal stage excludes energy penalties associated with pressure drop, exothermic adsorption, or bed regeneration, whereas these contributions are explicitly included in the present study and significantly increase the overall energy demand. Furthermore, their assumption of cooling water available at 15°C improves compressor energy efficiency and allows CO_2 condensation in the final high-pressure distillation step without refrigeration expenses. By contrast, in this work, the partial condenser duty of $1.86 \text{ MW}_{\text{th}}$ is supplied by heat recovered from CO_2 melting, which is therefore unavailable for cooling in the MSHX, raising the power demand of the Refrigerant 1 loop. Additional differences include the turbomachinery efficiencies of 90% and heat exchangers pinch temperatures of 2°C adopted by Asgharian et al. (2025), which enhance the process efficiency, but may not be representative of real industrial systems. Finally, the two studies employ different thermodynamic frameworks, leading to variations in phase equilibria and energy balances calculations that further contribute to the discrepancy in energy demand estimates.

The overall energy balance for CCC-90 and CCC-95 is reported in Table 7, which summarises the enthalpy flows of all inlet and outlet streams as well as the electrical power consumption of the process units discussed above. The energy balance closes with a minimal relative error ($1.6 \cdot 10^{-6}$ for CCC-90 and $6.6 \cdot 10^{-6}$ for CCC-95), confirming the consistency and reliability of the process model. For both configurations, the breakdown of the thermal duties exchanged in all heat exchangers, as well as detailed stream properties, including material balances for each component, are provided in Tables S11-S14 of the Supplementary Material.

Table 7. Energy balance on the overall control volume for the optimal cryogenic capture process at 90% capture rate (CCC-90) and 95% capture rate (CCC-95), as shown in Figure 5.

		CCC-90	CCC-95
IN			
Enthalpy flow flue gas (stream #1)	MW _{th}	-339.81	-339.81
Enthalpy flow isopentane (stream #36)	MW _{th}	-0.05	-0.05
Enthalpy flow cooling water	MW _{th}	-17799.58	-18704.21
Power consumption process units	MW _{el}	31.26	33.41
Total	MW	-18108.18	-19010.66
OUT			
Enthalpy flow CO ₂ (stream #31)	MW _{th}	-240.10	-253.44
Enthalpy flow lean gas (stream #20)	MW _{th}	-54.19	-41.14
Enthalpy flow water DCC (stream #10)	MW _{th}	-1834.64	-1834.39
Enthalpy flow water DRY 1 (stream #12)	MW _{th}	-12.43	-12.47
Enthalpy flow cooling water	MW _{th}	-15966.85	-16869.35
Total	MW	-18108.21	-19010.79
Difference	MW	0.03	0.13

3.1.1 Sensitivity analyses on energy penalty

Sensitivity analyses were conducted to evaluate the energy performance of the CCC process across varying flue gas compositions and *CCR*, focusing on the resulting energy penalty. For each case, the process was re-optimised following the approach outlined in Section 2.6, while the assumptions described in Section 2.4 were retained unless otherwise specified.

The reference condition considers flue gas from a coal-fired cement plant with a CO₂ concentration of 22.2%_{mol}. In practice, cement plants typically exhibit concentrations in the range 13-28%_{mol}, depending on fuel type, air leakage level, and raw meal moisture (Hughes et al., 2024). To reflect this variability, the energy penalty was evaluated as a function of CO₂ concentration (Figure 7). The latter was varied arbitrarily across the range 13-28%_{mol}, while the relative fractions of other components were renormalised. The analysis was conducted maintaining a 90% *CCR* by adjusting the isopentane flow to the desublimation exchanger (stream #21 in Figure 5), while the SLURRY COOLER outlet temperature (stream #24 in Figure 5) was fixed at -124°C.

As shown in Figure 7a, the energy penalty exhibits a decreasing trend from 1.41 to 1.12 MJ_{el}/kgCO₂ across the investigated range. The process performs efficiently for CO₂ concentrations down to

approximately 17%_{mol}, as the energy penalty is still below 1.30 MJ_{el}/kgCO₂ (9% above the base case). This indicates that CCC can effectively reduce emissions even in plants with higher air leakage or partial substitution of conventional fuels, which typically yield flue gas concentrations of 17-19%_{mol}.

Figure 7. Sensitivity analysis of cryogenic capture energy penalty as a function of CO₂ concentration in the flue gas. (a) Energy penalty and minimum temperature desublimation trends; (b) Energy penalty breakdown across Refrigerant 1 compressor, blower + e-heater, and other sources.

Although a comparison with other technologies is challenging due to differing process boundaries and assumptions, literature data for MEA-based capture provide a useful benchmark. For instance, Voldsund et al. (2019) reported 3.80 MJ_{th}/kgCO₂ plus 0.55 MJ_{el}/kgCO₂ for a flue gas containing 18%_{mol} CO₂ at 90% capture, while Cremona et al. (2025) estimated 3.85 MJ_{th}/kgCO₂ and 0.60 MJ_{el}/kgCO₂ for a 15%_{mol} CO₂ stream at 95% capture. These outcomes suggest that CCC energy requirements would remain substantially lower than those of MEA-based systems, even for more diluted flue gases.

Figure 7b highlights that the specific energy demand of the Refrigerant 1 loop and the drying section (BLOWER and e-HEATER) decreases as the inlet CO₂ concentration increases. In contrast, the contribution of miscellaneous components, including pumps, CO₂ compression, and the Refrigerant 2 compressor, remains constant. At higher CO₂ concentrations, the minimum temperature in the desublimation exchanger rises, and less energy is wasted to cool gas other than CO₂. Both effects decrease the isopentane demand per unit of CO₂ captured and consequently lower the energy penalty associated with the Refrigerant 1 compressor. Additionally, a larger CO₂ concentration increases flue

gas density, which reduces specific power requirements for the BLOWER. Since the e-HEATER maintains a constant electrical demand regardless of inlet concentration, the specific energy required for drying drops considerably.

The sensitivity of the energy penalty to the *CCR* was investigated across the 85-99% range (Figure 8), by adjusting the SLURRY COOLER outlet temperature while keeping the flowrate of isopentane to the desublimation exchanger fixed at the CCC-90 value of 289.6 kg/s.

Figure 8. Sensitivity analysis of cryogenic capture energy penalty as a function of CO_2 capture rate. (a) Energy penalty and minimum temperature desublimation trends; (b) Energy penalty breakdown across Refrigerant 1 compressor, blower + e-heater, and other sources.

As shown in Figure 8a, the energy penalty remains relatively stable between 85% and 95% capture, ranging from 1.18 to 1.21 MJ_{el}/kg_{CO2}. Beyond 95%, it rises more steeply, reaching 1.33 MJ_{el}/kg_{CO2} at 99%. This trend is explained by the breakdown in Figure 8b. As the *CCR* increases, the minimum temperature in the desublimation exchanger decreases, requiring the isopentane to be cooled to lower temperatures in the SLURRY COOLER. This results in greater specific energy demand in the Refrigerant 1 loop. In contrast, the energy requirements of the drying section remain constant in absolute terms; hence, its specific contribution decreases as more CO_2 is captured. These two opposing effects counterbalance each other up to around 93-95% capture, above which the Refrigerant 1 energy demand becomes increasingly dominant. The analysis highlights that increasing

the *CCR* from 90% to 95% results in a marginal rise in energy penalty, since a fixed amount of energy must be spent on flue gas drying regardless of the capture level.

3.2 CO₂ emissions assessment

A comparison of the CO₂ emissions-related KPIs between the reference cement plant and the plant equipped with CCC is presented in Table 8. For benchmarking purposes, the performance of the combined calciner electrification and MEA-based capture system (eCalc-MEA), investigated in the authors' previous work (Varnier et al., 2025), is also included. Specifically, the Ent-RMP configuration, identified as the most economically favourable alternative, is considered. Although this comparison is not entirely equivalent, given that eCalc-MEA represents an integrated decarbonisation approach requiring substantial modifications to the conventional plant layout, it offers a valuable benchmark for evaluating the environmental performance of fully electrified technologies in the cement sector.

The implementation of the CCC process increases electricity consumption by a factor of 2.88 and 3.01 compared to the reference plant for CCC-90 and CCC-95, respectively. Under the EU-27 energy mix scenario, this significant rise in electricity demand reduces equivalent CO₂ avoidance rates (AC_{eq}) to 79.1% and 83.4%, due to the indirect emissions associated with electricity generation. In comparison, the eCalc-MEA configuration shows an even more pronounced increase in electricity demand, approximately 7 times greater than the reference plant. As a result, despite achieving a higher *CCR*, its AC_{eq} is lower than that of CCC-90 and CCC-95.

The comparison shifts under a renewable electricity supply scenario. In the absence of indirect emissions, the AC_{eq} of CCC-90 and CCC-95 equals their respective *CCR*, as expected for post-combustion technologies. In this context, the eCalc-MEA achieves an AC_{eq} exceeding 98%, benefiting from both a high *CCR* and a reduction in generated CO₂ through partial replacement of thermal fuel with electric heating.

Table 8. Summary of environmental key performance indicators for reference cement plant (Varnier et al., 2025) and fully electrified low-carbon solutions under different scenarios for the carbon intensity of electricity. CCC-90: cryogenic CO₂ capture at 90% capture rate; CCC-95: cryogenic CO₂ capture at 95% capture rate; eCalc-MEA: combined calciner electrification and MEA-based capture system (Varnier et al., 2025).

		Reference plant	CCC-90	CCC-95	eCalc-MEA
Direct fuel consumption	GJ _{LHV} /t _{clk}	3.13	3.13	3.13	1.04
Electric power consumption ($W_{el,clk}$)	MWh _{el} /t _{clk}	0.132	0.380	0.397	0.920
CO ₂ captured ($e_{capt,clk}$)	kg _{CO2} /t _{clk}	0.0	749.8	791.5	630.0
Direct CO ₂ emissions (e_{clk})	kg _{CO2} /t _{clk}	833.1	83.3	41.7	15.5
CO ₂ outlet purity	% mol	-	99.9%	99.9%	97.7%
Carbon capture rate (CCR)	%	-	90.0%	95.0%	97.6%
EU-27 energy mix in 2022 ($e_{el} = 258 \text{ kg}_{\text{CO}_2}/\text{MWh}_{\text{el}}$)					
Indirect CO ₂ emissions ($e_{clk,el}$)	kg _{CO2} /t _{clk}	34.0	98.0	102.4	237.3
Equivalent CO ₂ emissions ($e_{clk,eq}$)	kg _{CO2} /t _{clk}	867.1	181.3	144.0	252.8
Equivalent CO₂ avoidance (AC_{eq})	%	-	79.1%	83.4%	70.8%
Non-combustible renewables ($e_{el} = 0 \text{ kg}_{\text{CO}_2}/\text{MWh}_{\text{el}}$)					
Indirect CO ₂ emissions ($e_{clk,el}$)	kg _{CO2} /t _{clk}	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
Equivalent CO ₂ emissions ($e_{clk,eq}$)	kg _{CO2} /t _{clk}	833.1	83.3	41.7	15.5
Equivalent CO₂ avoidance (AC_{eq})	%	-	90.0%	95.0%	98.1%

3.3 Economic results

The breakdown of total plant cost (*TPC*) across different equipment categories for the CCC-90 and CCC-95 configurations is shown in Figure 9. Both alternatives require significantly higher capital investment compared to the reference plant, whose *TPC* is estimated at 271 M€ (Varnier et al., 2025). This reference value is omitted from Figure 9 to emphasise better the differences between the two CCC options. The estimated *TPC* is 183 M€ for CCC-90 (approximately 67% of a new cement plant CAPEX) and 189 M€ for CCC-95 (about 70%).

Figure 9. Breakdown of total plant cost (TPC) associated with the cryogenic capture process at 90% capture rate (CCC-90) and 95% capture rate (CCC-95).

In both cases, the Refrigerant 1 compressor is the largest contributor to CAPEX, accounting for 48-49% of the TPC. This is followed by heat exchangers, including the MSHX, which represent 16% of the total. The drying section, comprising the columns, molecular sieve and electric heater, contributes 12%, while the BLOWER accounts for an additional 9%.

The incremental CAPEX required to increase the CCR from 90% to 95% is relatively small, amounting to 6.3 M€ (+3.4%). This increase reflects the need for larger compressors and pumps to handle higher refrigerants and CO₂ flowrates, as well as larger heat exchangers to meet the increased cooling demand. The only component showing a cost reduction in CCC-95 is the MSHX. Higher refrigerant flowrates lead to more favourable heat transfer coefficients and temperature gradients; hence, despite the increased overall duty, a slightly smaller MSHX volume is required.

The breakdown of the increment in cost of clinker (ΔCOC) for the CCC-90 and CCC-95 configurations is presented in Figure 10a. The ΔCOC is estimated at 87.6 €/t_{clik} for the CCC-90 and 92.1 €/t_{clik} for CCC-95. Compared to the baseline production cost of 79.8 €/t_{clik} estimated for the reference unabated plant (Varnier et al., 2025), the implementation of the CCC-90 and CCC-95

represents an increase of 110% and 115%, respectively. The difference between CCC-90 and CCC-95 is modest (+5.1%) and primarily reflects the higher CO₂ flowrate captured and processed in CCC-95, which leads to increased CAPEX, electricity demand, and transportation and storage costs.

Figure 103. Breakdown of (a) increment in cost of clinker and (b) cost of avoided CO₂ associated with the cryogenic capture process at 90% capture rate (CCC-90) and 95% capture rate (CCC-95).

In both cases, variable OPEX is the dominant cost component, accounting for approximately 67% of the ΔCOC , while the annualised CAPEX contributes around 21%. Within the variable OPEX, electricity is the largest contributor, representing 35.4% and 36.0% of the ΔCOC for CCC-90 and CCC-95, respectively. CO₂ transportation and storage also have a significant impact, accounting for 30% of the total, while cooling water and isopentane make-up have a marginal effect.

Figure 10b shows the corresponding cost of avoided CO₂ (*CAC*) breakdown. Since *CAC* is calculated directly from ΔCOC , the same cost distribution trends apply. The *CAC* values for both configurations are nearly identical: 127.7 €/t_{CO2} for CCC-90 and 127.4 €/t_{CO2} for CCC-95. The slightly lower *CAC* in the 95% capture case reflects the larger amount of equivalent CO₂ emissions avoided, which offsets its higher cost.

Given the similar *CAC* outcomes and the typical focus in the literature on 90% capture, CCC-90 is used for economic benchmarking against other low-carbon technologies. Comparison technologies include MEA-based capture, tail-end calcium looping (Tail-end-CaL), oxyfuel process, and electrified calciner combined with MEA capture system (eCalc-MEA), as shown in Figure 11. The reference cost values for MEA, Tail-end-CaL, and oxyfuel are based on CEMCAP project data (De Lena et al., 2019; Gardarsdottir et al., 2019; Voldsund et al., 2019), while figures for eCalc-MEA were sourced from a previous study (Varnier et al., 2025)².

Figure 114. Comparison of cost of CO₂ avoided between cryogenic capture at 90% capture rate (CCC-90), MEA-based capture (MEA), oxyfuel cement process, tail-end calcium looping (Tail-end-CaL) and electrified calciner combined with MEA (eCalc-MEA). Results are adapted from De Lena et al. (2019); Gardarsdottir et al. (2019); Voldsund et al. (2019); Varnier et al. (2025), and recomputed using the same economic assumptions as this study.

Among the post-combustion technologies, CCC-90 demonstrates strong economic competitiveness.

It significantly outperforms the conventional steam-regenerated MEA system, mainly due to its lower operating costs. The MEA system requires a large amount of steam for solvent regeneration, which

² All CAPEX figures were updated to 2024 using CEPCI, and the same rates for indirect costs, project contingencies, and owner's costs as in this study were applied. Variable OPEX were recalculated according to the economic assumptions detailed in Table 4 and Supplementary Table S9. Transport and storage costs were included to ensure a consistent comparison, especially for Tail-end-CaL, which produces and captures more CO₂ and incurs higher associated costs.

is produced by a natural gas boiler. This results in large OPEX and additional CO₂ emissions, reducing the net amount of equivalent CO₂ avoided.

In comparison to Tail-end-CaL, CCC-90 exhibits a *CAC* approximately 12% higher. Although Tail-end-CaL incurs greater CAPEX, coal usage, and transportation/storage expenses, it benefits from a lower net electricity consumption than the reference unabated plant. As such, the relative performance of CCC and Tail-end-CaL is highly dependent on the energy supply conditions. For example, with an electricity price of 90 €/MWh_{el} and a grid carbon intensity of 200 kg_{CO₂}/MWh_{el}, CCC-90 achieves a lower *CAC* than Tail-end-CaL (112.6 €/t_{CO₂} vs 116.3 €/t_{CO₂}).

When benchmarked against integrated decarbonisation approaches, CCC-90 is less cost-effective than oxyfuel, with a *CAC* 18% higher due to larger electricity demand and slightly higher CAPEX. Conversely, CCC-90 substantially outperforms the fully electrified eCalc-MEA alternative, with a *CAC* 71% lower. The latter suffers from prohibitively high electricity consumption, making it uncompetitive in scenarios where electricity is both carbon-intensive and expensive.

It is noteworthy that both oxyfuel and eCalc-MEA require extensive plant modifications, increasing technical risk and necessitating prolonged plant shutdowns. Post-combustion technologies, including CCC, MEA, and Tail-end-CaL, are more compatible with existing plant infrastructures and can be retrofitted with minimal disruption. Finally, CCC delivers CO₂ at a higher purity than all benchmarked options except for MEA, offering a potential advantage for downstream utilisation or sequestration.

3.3.1 Sensitivity analyses on economic performance

To assess the impact of key parameters on the *CAC* of the CCC-90 process, a sensitivity analysis was performed by examining the combined effects of electricity price, carbon intensity of imported electricity, and CAPEX variation. A three-level full factorial Design of Experiments was used to explore the parameter space defined in Table 9. A response surface model was then developed to

investigate the effects of individual factors, their interactions, and quadratic effects by estimating the associated regression coefficients.

Table 9. Factor levels of the Design of Experiments used for the sensitivity analysis.

Parameter		Low level	Intermediate level	High level
Electricity price	€/MWh _{el}	0	100	200
CO ₂ intensity electricity	kg _{CO2} /MWh _{el}	0	150	300
Δ CAPEX	%	-30	0	+30

The upper bounds for electricity price and carbon intensity reflect peak values recorded in Europe during 2022 (EEA, 2025; Eurostat, 2025). CAPEX uncertainty was assumed to range $\pm 30\%$, in line with the expected accuracy of AACE Class 4 cost estimates (AACE International, 2020).

The sensitivity results are presented in Figure 12, which shows contour plots of the *CAC* as a function of electricity price and CAPEX variation across four electricity carbon intensity levels, ranging from the baseline (258 kg_{CO2}/MWh_{el}) to a fully decarbonised electricity supply. *CAC* is directly proportional to all factors, with electricity price exerting the strongest effect, as indicated by the steep vertical orientation of the contour lines. CAPEX also plays a significant role, whereas the impact of carbon intensity is more moderate.

The plots illustrate how the interaction between key parameters influences *CAC* outcomes. At the baseline electricity carbon intensity (top-left plot) and nominal CAPEX, the *CAC* spans from 82 to 155 €/t_{CO2} across the range of electricity prices, representing a -35% to +21% deviation from the base case. At a more moderate electricity price and carbon intensity (100 €/MWh_{el} and 200 kg_{CO2}/MWh_{el}), aligned with the latest EU-27 projections (EEA, 2025; Eurostat, 2025), *CAC* varies between 104 and 128 €/t_{CO2} due to uncertainty in CAPEX evaluation (top-right plot).

From another perspective, these results identify parameter combinations that yield a certain *CAC* threshold. With a deeply decarbonised grid (100 kg_{CO2}/MWh_{el}, bottom-left plot), CCC-90 can achieve a *CAC* below 100 €/t_{CO2} for electricity prices in the range 30-97 €/MWh_{el}, depending on CAPEX accuracy. If CAPEX remains at the nominal level, the maximum electricity price that maintains *CAC* below this threshold is approximately 65 €/MWh_{el}.

The analysis can also provide practical insights into how regional electricity supply scenarios affect economic viability. For example, assuming that electricity is supplied from solar photovoltaics (carbon intensity: $0 \text{ kg}_{\text{CO}_2}/\text{MWh}_{\text{el}}$) in the Netherlands (levelised cost of electricity: $55 \text{ €/MWh}_{\text{el}}$; IRENA, 2024), CCC-90 yields a CAC of $94 \text{ €/t}_{\text{CO}_2}$ at baseline CAPEX, and $101 \text{ €/t}_{\text{CO}_2}$ with a 20% CAPEX increase.

Figure 52. Sensitivity analysis on the cost of avoided CO₂ varying electricity price, carbon intensity of electricity and plant CAPEX simultaneously, for the cryogenic capture process at 90% capture rate (CCC-90).

3.3 Discussion

The outcomes of this study highlight that CCC represents a promising solution compared to more conventional CO₂ capture technologies, demonstrating a competitive performance from both an

energy and economic perspective. Since the Refrigerant 1 loop contributes significantly to the overall power consumption, optimising its operating conditions is key to minimising the energy penalty. Further improvements could be achieved by adding refrigerant components, redesigning the refrigeration cycles, and jointly optimising the two loops. However, these strategies would increase process complexity, both in operation and optimisation. Replacing throttling valves with expansion turbines to recover compression energy is another option, but it would require higher CAPEX.

Although not examined in this work, ambient temperature could have a significant impact on cryogenic processes, as heat exchange with the environment affects both energy demand and overall economics. Assessing this effect would be an interesting extension of the present study.

A critical finding is the strong influence of the drying section on techno-economic performance, as it accounts for 21% of CAPEX and 17% of total power consumption. The associated energy penalty rapidly increases as CO₂ concentration in the flue gas decreases, making CCC particularly well suited to cement applications, where CO₂ levels are higher than in the power sector. Additionally, drying requirements remain nearly constant regardless of *CCR*, explaining why increasing capture from 90% to 95% has only a marginal impact on energy efficiency and economic performance. Further advances in drying section design are therefore essential to enhance CCC competitiveness.

The simplified modelling of the molecular sieve unit may lead to an underestimation of its CAPEX. The estimated *TPC* of 10.6 M€ for the molecular sieve corresponds to nearly half (47%) of the drying section CAPEX and about 6% of the entire plant, and therefore has some influence on the economics. For instance, assuming a molecular sieve CAPEX twice as large would increase the *TPC* to 193.6 M€ and 199.9 M€ for CCC-90 and CCC-95, respectively (+6% for both). However, the effect on ΔCOC and *CAC* would remain limited, with increases below 2%, due to the minor contribution of annualised CAPEX to these KPIs. Thus, even under conservative cost assumptions, the main conclusions of the study remain consistent.

With a *CAC* of 127-128 €/t_{CO₂}, CCC is considerably more cost-effective than MEA-based capture, the conventional benchmark technology. Although oxyfuel and Tail-end-CaL appear more

economically favourable, CCC delivers CO₂ at higher purity and avoids the major process modifications required by oxyfuel implementation.

From a policy perspective, ensuring the economic viability of CCC in the current European context would require carbon prices of at least 130 €/tCO₂, which is approximately double the values observed in the EU carbon market in early 2025 (60-80 €/tCO₂; Ember, 2025). As with any fully electrified decarbonisation technology, access to affordable and low-carbon electricity is decisive for cost-effectiveness. The sensitivity analysis indicates that *CAC* could fall below 100 €/tCO₂ if the imported electricity is further decarbonised (below 100 kgCO₂/MWh_{el}) and prices remain under 65 €/MWh_{el}, conditions aligned with renewable-dominated energy systems (IRENA, 2024). Targeted subsidies for renewable energy deployment within cement plants could therefore accelerate the adoption of fully electrified decarbonisation technologies by offsetting investment costs and lowering energy-related expenses.

4. Conclusions

This study investigated the techno-economic potential of cryogenic CO₂ capture for low-carbon cement production. Two process configurations targeting 90% and 95% capture of direct CO₂ emissions with a purity of 99.9%_{mass} were designed, optimised, and benchmarked against alternative decarbonisation technologies. The optimisation focused on minimising energy demand by tuning the composition, condensation pressure and temperature of a mixed-refrigerant loop, while maintaining the minimum temperature approach in heat exchangers.

A key contribution of this work is the development of a thermodynamic framework capable of accurately predicting both phase equilibria and specific heat capacities in cryogenic CO₂ capture applications. This was achieved using the volume-translated Peng-Robinson (VTPR) equation of state combined with a refitted α -function, calibrated to vapour pressure and liquid heat capacity data.

The fully electric cryogenic CO₂ capture process demonstrated high energy efficiency. At 90% capture, the energy penalty reached 1.19 MJ_{el}/kgCO₂, significantly lower than a conventional MEA-based capture. Refrigerant compression (74%) and flue-gas drying (17%) – including compression and molecular-sieve regeneration – were the dominant contributors to energy demand, highlighting the importance of optimising the refrigeration cycle and drying section. In the proposed design, complete water removal was achieved through cooling and chilled water scrubbing, followed by a molecular sieve regenerated electrically. The process also showed efficient performance across a range of flue gas CO₂ concentration, maintaining an energy penalty below 1.30 MJ_{el}/kgCO₂ for concentrations typical of cement flue gas (17-28%_{mol}).

Increasing the capture rate beyond 90% proved particularly attractive, enabling higher CO₂ avoidance with minimal impact on energy and economic performance. Between 90% and 95% capture, the energy penalty remained nearly constant (1.19-1.21 MJ_{el}/kgCO₂), while equivalent CO₂ avoidance rates rose from 79.1% to 83.4% under an EU-27 energy mix. At 90% capture, the increment in cost of clinker was estimated at 87.6 €/t_{clk} (+110% with respect to the unabated cement plant), which increased by 5% at 95% capture. Nevertheless, the cost of avoided CO₂ was approximately 127 €/tCO₂ in both cases, as the higher emissions avoided balanced the greater clinker production cost.

From an economic perspective, cryogenic capture substantially outperformed both conventional MEA-based capture and MEA-based capture combined with calciner electrification. Although slightly less cost-effective than tail-end calcium looping and oxyfuel, it offers the advantages of delivering higher CO₂ purity and the potential for retrofit with minimal process disruption. Sensitivity analyses further evidenced that cryogenic capture becomes highly competitive in scenarios with low-carbon (<100 kgCO₂/MWh_{el}) and moderately costly electricity (<65 €/MWh_{el}).

While further advances in the design of the drying section and refrigeration cycles could reduce the energy penalty and improve cost-effectiveness, cryogenic capture already emerges as a promising option for cement plants. Depending on local energy supply and infrastructure, this technology has

the potential to compete with more established options, offering a viable pathway for large-scale decarbonisation of the cement industry.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Leonardo Varnier: Conceptualisation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Methodology, Software, Visualisation, Writing – original draft. **Federico d’Amore:** Methodology, Supervision, Validation, Writing – review and editing. **Bart de Groot:** Software, Writing – review and editing. **Fabrizio Bezzo:** Methodology, Supervision, Writing – review and editing, Funding acquisition.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests: B.d.G is an employee of Siemens Industry Software Limited.

Declaration of Generative AI and AI-assisted technologies in the writing process

During the preparation of this work, the authors used generative AI to improve the readability and language of the manuscript. After using this tool, the authors reviewed and edited the content as needed and take full responsibility for the content of the published article.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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Nomenclature

Acronyms

BAT		Best available technique
CaL		Calcium looping
CAPEX		Capital cost
CCC		Cryogenic CO ₂ capture
CCS		Carbon capture and storage
KPIs		Key performance indicators
MEA		Monoethanolamine
MSHX		Multi-stream heat exchanger
NLPMSO		Non-Linear Programming Multi-Start Optimiser
PR		Peng-Robinson
SLE		Solid-liquid equilibria
SLVE		Solid-liquid-vapour equilibria
SQP		Sequential Quadratic Programming
TSA		Temperature swing adsorption
VLE		Vapour-liquid equilibria
VTPR		Volume-translated Peng-Robinson

Symbols

α	–	α -function of cubic equations of state
γ	MJ _{el} /kgCO ₂	Energy penalty
ΔCOC	€/t _{clik}	Increment in cost of clinker
ΔT_{min}	K	Minimum temperature approach
AC_{eq}	%	Equivalent CO ₂ avoided

<i>BEC</i>	€	Bare erected cost
<i>c</i>	–	Parameter of the ideal gas heat capacity function
<i>CAC</i>	€/t _{CO₂}	Cost of avoided CO ₂
<i>CCR</i>	%	Carbon capture rate
<i>c_p</i>	J/mol/K	Heat capacity
<i>EC</i>	€	Equipment cost
<i>e_{capt,clk}</i>	kg _{CO₂} /t _{clk}	Specific CO ₂ captured
<i>e_{clk}</i>	kg _{CO₂} /t _{clk}	Direct specific CO ₂ emissions
<i>e_{el}</i>	kg _{CO₂} /MWh _{el}	Carbon intensity of the imported electricity
<i>e_{el,clk}</i>	kg _{CO₂} /t _{clk}	Indirect specific CO ₂ emissions
<i>e_{eq,clk}</i>	kg _{CO₂} /t _{clk}	Equivalent specific CO ₂ emissions
<i>i</i>	%	Discount rate
<i>IF</i>	–	Installation factor
<i>j</i>	–	Generic process unit
<i>l</i>	–	Parameter of α-function
<i>m_{clk}</i>	t _{clk} /y	Annual clinker productivity
<i>m_{CO₂,capt}</i>	kg _{CO₂} /s	Mass flowrate of captured CO ₂
<i>ML</i>	€/y	Maintenance labour cost
<i>n</i>	y	Plant operational life
<i>OL</i>	€/y	Operating labour cost
<i>OPEX</i>	€/y	Operative costs
<i>p^{sat}</i>	bar	Vapour pressure
<i>T</i>	K	Temperature
<i>TAC</i>	€/y	Total annualised CAPEX
<i>TDC</i>	€	Total direct cost

TOC	€	Total overnight cost
TPC	€	Total plant cost
\dot{W}_{el}^{CCC}	MW _{el}	Electrical power consumed cryogenic CO ₂ capture
$\dot{W}_{el,clk}$	MWh _{el} /t _{clk}	Overall electrical energy consumption

Sub-/Superscripts

CCC	Plant with cryogenic CO ₂ capture
clk	Clinker
cr	Critical
el	Electric
eq	Equivalent
ig	Ideal gas
liq	Liquid
mass	By mass
mol	By mole
ref	Reference unabated plant
sat	Saturation
th	Thermal

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